

Autonomous Aerial Refueling Based on the Tanker Reference Frame

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Abstract—An aircraft formation autopilot is designed for flight test to demonstrate autonomous aerial refueling^{1,2}. The controller requirements are stated, and models for the lead and wing aircraft are outlined and stabilized. Control laws are developed for the model, and four frames of reference are investigated for optimal control. Next, a simulation is constructed with modeled disturbances to produce the real-time inputs that will be available to the controller. Results from simulations of the controller are presented and assessed, including an exploration of sensitivity and robustness. Finally, results are presented from a limited flight test investigation conducted with a formation of an Air Force C-12 and a variable stability Learjet LJ-25, flown by the controller. Fully autonomous aerial refueling maneuvers were successfully demonstrated in both level and turning flight. Finally, conclusions and lessons learned from the flight test and the controller development are presented.

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1. INTRODUCTION

Automated aerial refueling is of great interest to the Air Force, and the subject of current research and development by both the Air Force and commercial industry. Short term applications center around unmanned combat aerial vehicles (UCAVs), specifically, the Joint Unmanned Combat Air System (J-UCAS). Aerial refueling will increase UCAV deployment capability, remove transportation vehicle

requirements, decrease dependence on in-theater land operations, and greatly extend range and station time. The National Aeronautics and Space Administration (NASA) has demonstrated limited formation station keeping capability (controlling only elevator and ailerons) during non-turning flight [1]. The US Air Force Test Pilot School (TPS) has also demonstrated limited success with close formation control, using a simulated lead aircraft [2].

Figure 1 - Test Aircraft Approaching Contact Position

The scope of this research is limited to a specific Test Management Project (TMP) that occurred at the Test Pilot School during October, 2005, with two test aircraft [3]. The controller was designed as a thesis project for the Air Force Institute of Technology (AFIT) [4]. The controller was installed on a Calspan owned Learjet LJ-25 with a Variable Stability System (VSS) capable of driving the control surfaces and the throttle with external inputs. Both the lead and wing aircraft were equipped with a carrier phase differential AFIT Relative Navigation Global Positioning System (GPS), also designed as an AFIT thesis project. The lead aircraft was also equipped with a small Micro-Electrical Mechanical System Inertial Measurement Unit (MEMS IMU) for attitude measurements. A commercial Freewave data link system was installed on both aircraft to transmit the relative position and attitude parameters of the lead aircraft (a C-12 simulating a tanker) to the trail aircraft (the Learjet, simulating a receiver).

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The controller design was limited. The gains were optimized specifically for control of the Learjet at one design airspeed and altitude, though some flight test was done at a higher altitude to minimize turbulence. Control parameters and feedback variables were selected from a limited set of sensor inputs available in real-time and do not necessarily reflect optimal control. In addition, based on the previous work of Hall [5] and Proud [6], the controller was assumed to have the control authority and robustness to overcome effects from the vortex field of the lead aircraft, and these were neglected. Finally, only maneuvers and formation positions required for aerial refueling were investigated. Rejoin and departure from the tanker were not considered.

To perform aerial refueling, the controller must have the capability of maintaining and moving between the contact, pre-contact, and wing observations during straight and level flight and during turns. The formation positions are shown in Figure 2, and the displacement vectors are defined in the tanker body frame (discussed in Section 3) and indicated in feet. The ranges are based on the distance between the rear GPS antenna on a modified KC-135 tanker (just forward of the tail on the upper surface of the empennage), and the center GPS antenna on the J-UCAS. The fact that the actual test aircraft were smaller made the distances seem slightly exaggerated, but the spacing was retained for realism since the larger lever arm increased the difficulty of control.

Figure 2 - Refueling Formation Positions

A design goal of station keeping within 10 feet during all maneuvers in any direction with collision potential was set for the pre-contact and wing observation positions. The more stringent limits of the contact position were defined by the physical limits of the refueling boom on a KC-135, shown in Figure 3.

Essentially, the boom is capable of moving in and out 6 feet, and 10 degrees up and down. Tanker maneuvers during refueling are simple. Oval “race track” patterns are flown with straight legs and 15° banked turns at the ends. Turns with up to 30° of bank may be used if airspace limitations arise.

Figure 3 – KC-135 Boom Limits.

2. AIRCRAFT MODELS

The formation model is inherently non-linear. The entire premise of control rests on maintaining angles and relative motion of aircraft moving and rotating in separate coordinate axis systems. The trigonometry is unavoidable, and multiple transformations are required with angles that are not necessarily small. Control surface position and rate saturation effects also must be included for realistic modeling. In addition, the goal is very precise control of an aircraft in a dynamic environment. Smaller effects that are normally linearized or neglected such as moments of inertia, axis coupling, and nose droop during roll-ins are now significant. As a result, full, non-linear models with six-degrees-of-freedom were used for both aircraft.

Initially, the flying portion of the TMP was proposed as F-16 vs. F-16, with the controller installed on the Calspan F-16 VISTA Stability Demonstrator. For scheduling and cost considerations, the Learjet was later designated as the wing aircraft and a USAF C-12 (Beechcraft King Air) was selected as the lead aircraft. At the time of the change, however, the lead stabilization and autopilot design work had already been performed on an F-16, and this model was retained. Though not ideal, the benign maneuvers of the flight lead (straight and level flight and turns with 15° or 30° of bank) make the compromise acceptable.

The widely different flight envelopes of the C-12 and the Learjet required changing the test design point from the true J-UCAS refueling condition of 25,000 feet mean sea level (MSL) and 275 knots indicated airspeed (KIAS), to 10,000 feet MSL and 190 KIAS, a point the C-12 can reach. The impact of the change is reduced performance from the wing

aircraft, which is near the low end of its airspeed spectrum for the clean configuration.

The wing aircraft model was obtained from Calspan, and is proprietary. The model for the lead aircraft, however, is very similar and is expounded. The lead model was taken from Stevens and Lewis [7], and the reader is directed there for stability derivatives, look-up tables, and other specifics. The overlying modeling technique follows the development of Nelson [8], and consists of solving for the dimensionalized forces and moments on the aircraft in the body frame with:

$$Lift = -Z = \bar{q}SC_L \quad (1)$$

$$Drag = -X = \bar{q}SC_D \quad (2)$$

$$Sideforce = Y = \bar{q}SC_Y \quad (3)$$

$$Rolling\ Moment = L = C_l \bar{q}Sb \quad (4)$$

$$Pitching\ Moment = M = C_m \bar{q}S\bar{c} \quad (5)$$

$$Yawing\ Moment = N = C_n \bar{q}Sb \quad (6)$$

using stability derivatives provided by General Dynamics for the wing model and from Stevens and Lewis [7] for the lead model as well as the dimensionless force and moment coefficients. The retained terms were:

$$C_L = C_{L_0} + C_{L_q} q \left(\frac{\bar{c}}{2u_0} \right) + C_{L_\alpha} \alpha + C_{L_{\dot{\alpha}}} \dot{\alpha} \quad (7)$$

$$C_D = C_{D_0} + C_{D_q} q \left(\frac{\bar{c}}{2u_0} \right) + C_{D_\alpha} \alpha + C_{D_{\dot{\alpha}}} \dot{\alpha} \quad (8)$$

$$C_Y = C_{Y_0} + C_{Y_r} r \left(\frac{1}{u_0} \right) + C_{Y_\beta} \beta + C_{Y_{\dot{\beta}}} \dot{\beta} \quad (9)$$

$$C_l = C_{l_p} \left(\frac{pb}{2u_0} \right) + C_{l_r} \left(\frac{rb}{2u_0} \right) + C_{l_\beta} \beta + C_{l_{\dot{\alpha}}} \dot{\alpha} + C_{l_{\dot{\beta}}} \dot{\beta} \quad (10)$$

$$C_n = C_{n_p} \left(\frac{pb}{2u_0} \right) + C_{n_r} \left(\frac{rb}{2u_0} \right) + C_{n_\beta} \beta + C_{n_{\dot{\alpha}}} \dot{\alpha} + C_{n_{\dot{\beta}}} \dot{\beta} \quad (11)$$

$$C_m = C_{m_q} \left(\frac{q\bar{c}}{2u_0} \right) + C_{m_{\dot{\alpha}}} \left(\frac{\dot{\alpha}\bar{c}}{2u_0} \right) + C_{m_\alpha} \alpha + C_{m_{\dot{\alpha}}} \dot{\alpha} \quad (12)$$

Angular velocities in the body frame (p , q , and r) were propagated with products and moments of inertia and the moment equations:

$$L = I_{xx} \dot{p} - I_{xz} \dot{r} + qr(I_{zz} - I_{yy}) - I_{xz} pq \quad (13)$$

$$M = I_{yy} \dot{q} + rp(I_{xx} - I_{zz}) + I_{xz} (p^2 - r^2) \quad (14)$$

$$N = -I_{xz} \dot{p} + I_{zz} \dot{r} + pq(I_{yy} - I_{xx}) + I_{xz} qr \quad (15)$$

Aircraft attitude was defined in terms of the Euler angles (ψ ,

θ , ϕ), and propagated through:

$$p = \dot{\phi} - \dot{\psi} \sin \theta \quad (16)$$

$$q = \dot{\theta} \cos \phi + \dot{\psi} \cos \theta \sin \phi \quad (17)$$

$$r = \dot{\psi} \cos \theta \cos \phi - \dot{\theta} \sin \phi \quad (18)$$

Finally, the aircraft's velocities in the body frame (u , v , w) were propagated with:

$$X - mg \sin \theta = m(\dot{u} + qw - rv) \quad (19)$$

$$Y + mg \cos \theta \sin \phi = m(\dot{v} + ru - pw) \quad (20)$$

$$Z + mg \cos \theta \cos \phi = m(\dot{w} + pv - qu) \quad (21)$$

In order to take advantage of modern design techniques, a linearized version of the lead model was used for stabilization and autopilot design, and the resulting gains were applied to the full model. The controls for the lead aircraft consisted of the throttle, elevator, ailerons, and rudder. Actual control surface angle was found by applying a first order lag model with a time constant of $\tau=1/20.2$ for actuator dynamics to the commands. The elevator angle and throttle position commands (δe_{cmd} and δT_{cmd}) were found as the sum of the equilibrium value for flight at the test design point and a perturbation, used for control:

$$\delta e_{cmd} = \delta e_0 + \Delta \delta e_{cmd} \quad (22)$$

$$\delta T_{cmd} = \delta T_0 + \Delta \delta T_{cmd} \quad (23)$$

Lead Aircraft Stabilization and Control

For the lead aircraft, longitudinal stability was insufficient (the bare F-16 airframe is unstable). A pitch stability augmentation system (SAS) was installed via perturbation feed back of angle of attack ($\Delta\alpha$), pitch rate (q), and pitch angle ($\Delta\theta$). An additional loop with altitude perturbation (Δh) was closed to hold desired altitude, making the lead perturbation elevator angle ($\Delta \delta e_{L_cmd}$) control law:

$$\Delta \delta e_{L_cmd} = k_{\alpha_L} \Delta \alpha_L + k_{q_L} \Delta q_L + k_{\theta_L} \Delta \theta_L + k_{h_L} \Delta h_L \quad (24)$$

where the subscript L denotes the lead aircraft.

Velocity deviation was fed back into the throttle channel for an airspeed control loop, making the lead throttle control law:

$$\Delta \delta T_{L_cmd} = k_{vel_L} \Delta vel_L \quad (25)$$

Engine saturation effects are included as a lag state in the original F-16 model. As the required throttle changes for the lead aircraft are small, and the C-12 turboprop engines will have faster spool up times than the turbofan engine on the F-16 (especially at the slow design point), the

differences were disregarded.

The rudder command channel consists of proportional plus integral plus derivative (PID) control on sideslip angle (β) to assist in turn coordination.

The control law for commanded rudder deflection (δr_{L_cmd}) became:

$$\delta r_{L_cmd} = k_{p\beta_L}\beta + k_{i\beta_L}\int \beta dt + k_{D\beta_L}\dot{\beta} \quad (26)$$

The aileron channel was designed to mimic a tanker with a bank angle (ϕ) hold system, with bank angle commands generated outside of the simulation. A roll rate (p_L) feedback loop was added to achieve a reasonable approximation of a tanker's roll rate and to eliminate bank angle overshoot. Aileron command (δa_{L_cmd}) was determined with the following control law:

$$\delta a_{L_cmd} = k_{\phi_L}(\phi_{L_cmd} - \phi_L) + k_{p_L}p_L \quad (27)$$

The values selected for all lead aircraft gains are shown in Table 1 with altitude in feet, speed in ft/sec, and all angles in degrees.

Table 1. Lead Aircraft Gains

Gain	k_{α_L}	k_{q_L}	k_{θ_L}	k_{h_L}	k_{vel_L}	k_{ϕ_L}
Value	-.56	-.192	-3	-.8	.1	-.5
Gain	$k_{p_L} (\phi=15^\circ)$	$k_{p_L} (\phi=30^\circ)$	$k_{p\beta_L}$	$k_{i\beta_L}$	$k_{D\beta_L}$	
Value	-0.7	-1.3	-4	-1	-3	

For turns with 15° of bank, a maximum roll rate of 7.5 deg/sec was used, with some sloping of the bank step command to avoid an abrupt roll. This simulated the normal practice of a formation flight lead “telegraphing” the turn at the initiation and completion of a roll. A maximum rate of 10 deg/sec was used for the turns with 30° of bank. These gains were altered during the sensitivity and robustness investigation to achieve desired tanker profiles with higher roll rates and bank angles.

Wing Aircraft Stability

The wing aircraft's bare airframe longitudinal stability was found to be satisfactory. The lateral channel, however, showed excessive Dutch roll oscillation. A rudder doublet of 2 rad/s was used to excite the mode in Figure 4.

Figure 4 - Learjet Bare Airframe Lateral Response

Yaw rate and roll rate are poorly damped. To mirror the technique used currently in the industry, damping was

added

through sideslip rate feedback, making the wing aircraft rudder deflection (δr_{w_cmd}) control law:

$$\delta r_{w_cmd} = k_{sas} \dot{\beta} \quad (28)$$

where $k_{sas} = -1.2$ and the “w” denotes the wing aircraft.

The value for the feedback gain was selected to bring the damping factor from the Learjet’s bare airframe value of 0.0028 to 0.19, the minimum value specified by MIL-STD-1797 [9] for a Level 1 rating during Category A flight. The same rudder doublet is given again in Figure 5.

Figure 5 - Learjet with Dutch Roll SAS

The SAS feedback was later increased during flight test ($k_{sas} = -1.5$), as the minimum acceptable value for MIL-STD was found to still be slightly oscillatory.

The real time value for sideslip rate came from a filter applied to the sideslip sensor (β vane) on the Learjet. The same filter was used for all differentiating in this project (with the objective of some high frequency noise cancellation, if it existed). In the case of sideslip, the transfer function was:

$$\frac{\dot{\beta}(s)}{\beta(s)} = \frac{100^2 s}{(s + 100)^2} \quad (29)$$

3. SIMULATION DESIGN

Axes Definitions

Several coordinate system transformations were required for the full simulation to produce the differential vector that was available during flight. The differential GPS provided a relative vector from the C-12 to the Learjet, without regard to the formation’s actual position over the Earth. For simplification of this paper, the assumption is made that the

GPS system supplied this relative position vector in terms of north error, east error, and down error. This eliminates the requirement for transformation from the GPS Earth Centered, Earth Fixed (ECEF) Frame into local latitude, longitude, and altitude, as well as the transformation from local to the North, East, Down frame.

$$\mathbf{C}_b^w = \begin{bmatrix} c\alpha c\beta & s\beta & s\alpha c\beta \\ -c\alpha s\beta & c\beta & -s\alpha s\beta \\ -s\alpha & 0 & c\alpha \end{bmatrix} \quad (32)$$

The North, East, Down (NED) frame normally shows deviation from a defined local position. However, since the vector of interest is the relative position of the two aircraft, the origin of the frame moves with the lead aircraft. The z-axis is directed from the lead aircraft's center of gravity (cg) toward the center of the earth, orthogonal to the axes pointing north (x) and east (y).

Three coordinate frames were investigated for control. The first was a "formation frame" used for control by NASA [1]. The origin of the frame moves with the cg of the lead aircraft, and it is defined from the NED frame by a single rotation of lead aircraft heading angle (ψ) about the NED z-axis with the following direction cosine matrix:

$$\mathbf{C}_\psi = \begin{bmatrix} c\psi & s\psi & 0 \\ -s\psi & c\psi & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 1 \end{bmatrix} \quad (30)$$

where s denotes sine and c denotes cosine. The frame did not rotate with the lead aircraft's bank angle, and was not intended to be used for control during turning flight.

In addition to the formation frame, the aircraft body frames were investigated for possible frames of control. The body frames are also attached to each aircraft's center of gravity. The x-axis points through the nose, the y-axis through the right wing, and the z-axis through the floor of the aircraft in another right-handed orthogonal system. The body frame is obtained from the NED frame through sequential Euler rotations of heading angle (ψ) about the NED z-axis, pitch angle (θ) about the first interim y-axis (the "formation frame"), and roll angle (ϕ) about the second interim x-axis, also the body frame x-axis. The direction cosine matrix from NED to the body frame is:

$$\mathbf{C}_{NED}^b = \begin{bmatrix} c\theta c\psi & c\theta s\psi & -s\theta \\ s\phi s\theta c\psi - c\phi s\psi & s\phi s\theta s\psi + c\phi c\psi & s\phi c\theta \\ c\phi s\theta c\psi + s\phi s\psi & c\phi s\theta s\psi - s\phi c\psi & c\phi c\theta \end{bmatrix} \quad (31)$$

The final frame investigated was the wing wind axis. The wing wind axis is found from the wing aircraft's body axis with a negative rotation of angle of attack (α) around the body y-axis followed by a positive rotation of the sideslip angle (β) around the interim z-axis (also known as the stability frame). The DCM from body to wind frame is:

Each of these frames was either required for the simulation, or investigated as a control frame.

Simulation Overview

Components of the simulation were developed independently, and initial gain selection was performed using a fabricated lead aircraft profile with perfect airspeed and altitude control and perfectly coordinated turns. The concept of the full simulation is presented in a simplified form in Figure 6.

The lead aircraft was commanded independently. The lead aircraft velocity was split into north and east components using the lead aircraft heading angle. The velocity components were then integrated to yield position change since initialization. The wing aircraft is treated in a similar fashion, with an initial offset based on the GPS antenna locations in the selected starting formation position. The trajectory difference yields the equivalent signal of the GPS system: relative position from the tanker to the Learjet, in the NED frame.

Figure 6 - Simulation Concept

During refueling, the desired formation position for the wingman to fly is constant relative to the attitude of the tanker (as the tanker banks, the desired position moves). Therefore, the vector from the tanker to the desired position is constant when expressed in the tanker body frame. This *desired* position vector was hard-coded for each of the formation positions (shown in Figure 2), and moved between the hard-coded values during position changes.

The vector of *actual* relative position (tanker to Learjet) was rotated into the tanker body frame via the lead aircraft's Euler angles. The actual positive vector was then differenced with the desired position vector to produce an error vector, from the Learjet the desired position, in the tanker body frame. The components of the error vector are fed into the control laws, which generate actuator commands to make the corrections and eliminate the error.

The tanker body frame was the final selection as the control frame. For investigation of other frames of control, the scheme was modified. Desired position was rotated into NED (or ECEF) and the difference was taken to achieve an error vector in that frame for the GPS signal. The error vector was then rotated into the control frame of choice (wing body, wing wind, formation frame, etc). A benefit of the final selection of the tanker frame was a large simplification of the software path that was installed on the real Learjet, and the elimination of several angles required for the extra transformations (as well as the corresponding noise from the sensors that supplied those angles). All propagation was performed with a second order solver and a fixed time step of 0.01 seconds, the sample time of the VSS computer.

Turbulence Model

A turbulence model was applied to both aircraft, taken from an approximation of the Von Karman model, shown below. Random disturbances in angle of attack and angle of sideslip were generated using the differential equation:

$$\dot{\alpha}_{Turb}(t) = -2\left(\frac{u_0}{L}\right)\alpha_{Turb}(t) + \frac{2\sigma}{\sqrt{\pi Lu_0}}\varepsilon(t) \quad (33)$$

where,

- α_{Turb} = random disturbance in angle of attack, rad
- u_0 = airspeed, ft/s
- ε = Zero mean, unity covariance white noise

Scale length, L was determined by altitude:

$$L = \begin{cases} 200 \text{ ft at sea level} \\ 200 \rightarrow 2500 \text{ ft when } h \leq 2500 \text{ ft (Linearly Interpolate)} \\ 2500 \text{ ft when } h > 2500 \text{ ft} \end{cases} \quad (34)$$

and

$$\sigma = \begin{cases} 6 \text{ ft/s normal} \\ 15 \text{ ft/s in cumulous clouds} \\ 30 \text{ ft/s in thunderstorms} \end{cases} \quad (35)$$

The turbulence was considered a static field relative to the

speed of the aircraft, and the same gusts were applied to both the leader and wingman, with a delay for the aircraft in trail.

Noise

As will be shown in the control frame and control law sections, the controller is sensitive to noise, especially on the lead aircraft attitude parameters. Flight test data from a Cessna 172 sortie with the MEMS IMU was used to increase simulator fidelity. Bias for actual heading angle, bank angle, etc. was removed, and the residual noise was recorded and added directly to the lead aircraft attitude sensor signals during simulations. After the first formation test flight, the same technique was used to record and use flight test noise off of the specific test platforms.

4. CONTROL FRAME INVESTIGATION

The basic control scheme developed is simple: apply an error in position to a controller which determines commands to resolve the errors. The x-axis component of the error vector was applied to the throttle, y-axis component to the ailerons, and z-axis component to the elevator. Rudder is not normally commanded by the pilot during refueling, and control was limited to the SAS already developed for lateral damping.

Each potential control frame presented the error vector in different components to the controller. The question of which set was most suitable for control was investigated. Figure 7 is exaggerated to illustrate the problem. In each case, the wing aircraft has error between the current position and the desired position—on the wing of the tanker, marked with an “x.” The frame of reference determines what proportion of error goes into each control channel (throttle, aileron, and elevator), and in extreme cases the direction of control. From Figure 7, the wing body frame seems intuitively the best choice, as it is the only one commanding the correct direction of control (left aileron).

Figure 7 - Control Frame Differences

Technically, the wing *wind* axis was investigated rather than the wing *body* axis, as it identifies where the aircraft is actually going to go vice just where it is pointed. Though a minor point (equilibrium angle of attack (α) is only 12.5°), Figure 8 shows the potential situation where the body frame could command “go down” when the correct command from the wind frame is “go up.”

Figure 8 - Wing Wind vs. Body Axes

The aircraft responded well with wind axis control for small errors and slow corrections. However, as with each control frame, some difficulties were discovered during simulation. By definition, the amount of error component in the wind frame that will drive the control on each channel varies with the wing aircraft’s attitude. During maneuvers, the wing aircraft will be “fighting” to maintain position as the geometry of the formation changes. The wing rock associated with overshoots and settling keeps the amount of error in the y and z channels constantly swapping, often relatively rapidly. This was especially apparent during large lateral position deviations (such as during formation position changes, or in the pre-contact position (40 feet low) when the tanker rolls into a 30° of bank).

A smaller, secondary effect of the channel swapping occurred with the addition of derivative control. As lateral error develops (such as in a turn, for instance), the wing aircraft banks to correct the error. However, as soon as the wing aircraft begins to bank, the amount of error seen in the y-axis (aileron channel) immediately decreases, even if the tanker is still pulling away. The result is derivative control in the wrong direction, as the decrease in y-error caused by banking is seen by the controller as a correction to the

lateral error. The proportional control was able to override the command and still control the aircraft, but the response was less than optimum, and degraded as more maneuvering was required of the wing aircraft.

One method of minimizing the problem of error components swapping channels as the wing aircraft rolled was to keep the reference frame from rotating at all. NASA followed this approach with the “formation frame”. The formation frame stayed parallel to the ground and only rotated with the lead aircraft heading, which was kept relatively constant during testing. This frame did not require attitude information from the lead aircraft, but a flight test engineer had to hard-code the lead aircraft heading. Thus, it had the added benefit of eliminating attitude sensor noise from the controller inputs [1]. The drawback was the inability to turn, which could, in theory, have been overcome with real-time data from a lead aircraft heading sensor.

Since the z-axis of the formation frame was always pure vertical, the control essentially uses elevator as an altitude hold system (though the altitude to hold is relative to the lead aircraft). Since the error components do not change with wing attitude, but only with actual relative movement of the wing aircraft, the formation frame inputs to the controller are far more stable, usually resulting in better control. A large amount of the gain selection work for this controller was done with formation frame control.

The formation frame’s weakness lies in its misalignment with the bank angle of the formation during turns. NASA never intended their controller to be capable of turning. Figure 9 illustrates the problem. In the upper diagram, a real pilot would fly to the “x” using only elevator. The formation frame, however, sees error in both the y and z channels, and would apply control to both the elevator and to right turning aileron. Likewise, in the lower picture, a pilot would correct with only aileron. The formation frame, however, would again apply control in both elevator and aileron channels. The result is oscillation around the desired point before stabilizing, leading to larger settling times that become worse with increasing bank angles.

Figure 9 - Formation Frame Misalignment Difficulties

The final channel investigated, and eventually selected for control, was the tanker body frame. During actual air refueling, pilots visually receive position feedback in the tanker body frame through a set of lights on the belly of the tanker. These lights derive receiver location from the position of the refueling boom and signal the pilot (move up, down, forward, or aft). Control in the tanker body frame has several advantages. As long as the tanker and the wingman have nearly the same bank angle (and they should during refueling), the frame gives almost the same error components as the wing wind frame, without the instability that comes through the frame rotating as the wing aircraft fights for position. It works effectively as an “average wing wind frame,” very nearly aligned with the actual flight control surfaces, without the penalty of position error swapping channels during station keeping. In addition, the wing angles of ψ , θ , ϕ , α , and β are no longer required in transformations as they were in wind frame control, reducing sensor noise errors and simplifying the controller software. Also, since the tanker maneuvers slowly, the sensor noise on the angles that are still required can be heavily filtered. Bank angle changes should be slow (normal tanker rolls with receivers are on the order of 3 deg/s), and heading angle should also never change faster than a standard rate turn of 3 deg/s (even if the tanker used 30 degrees of bank instead of the planned 15 degrees). The change in pitch angle for a 30° turn is negligible.

The tanker frame is not perfect, since it is not exactly aligned with the axes of the actual flight control surfaces. Simulation, however, showed it to be the most capable under these specific circumstances. Any time the wing aircraft did not have the same bank angle as the tanker, some amount of control was misapplied, but simulation showed this to be a very minor effect. Flight test later confirmed this--the tanker and receiver rarely had a bank angle difference of more than 5 degrees. The biggest weakness of controlling with this paradigm is the sensitivity

to lead aircraft motion (or sensor noise that appears as motion). In the pre-contact position, the wing aircraft is approximately 100 ft away from the lead aircraft. A one degree oscillation in lead aircraft heading will cause the “desired position” to move a foot. A one foot move over .01 sec (the sample rate of the VSS computer) will be interpreted by the derivative portion of the control law as an exceptionally high rate of relative speed, and large control movements will be commanded. Obviously, noise in the lead attitude sensor will be detrimental to control. Again, the reason this control paradigm still works is the ability to apply heavy filtering to the sensor noise due to the benign maneuvering and slow real-life rotation rates of a tanker (especially relative to sensor noise).

5. CONTROL LAW DEVELOPMENT

The initial premise of the research was to build a controller based on proportional plus integral (PI) control on position error only. This method was investigated with step responses in each channel and found to be insufficient without damping. Derivative control was added on all channels. As mentioned, the only control on the rudder channel that was applied was for Dutch roll damping in the yaw SAS.

For the throttle channel, PID control alone was found to provide acceptable levels of performance. The throttle channel control consisted of commanding the wing perturbation thrust (Δdx_{w_cmd}) with the control law:

$$\Delta dx_{w_cmd} = k_{x_p} x_e + k_{x_d} \dot{x}_e + k_{x_i} \int x_e dt \quad (36)$$

where the subscript e denotes error in the depicted direction.

For simulation, the total thrust command was found by adding an equilibrium estimate for the flight condition, and applying a saturation to keep the command within engine limits. It is understood that there will likely be some error in the equilibrium estimate, which will vary based on weight, density altitude, etc. Simulation shows that realistic errors will be removed by integral action within a 10-15 second settling period after system initialization; however, the initialization technique later developed for actual implementation on the Learjet eliminated this consideration altogether. Total thrust was further processed by applying a first order lag model with pure time delay for the engine spool up and auto-throttle dynamics (the actual numbers are proprietary).

For implementation on the Learjet, a “freeze and hold” technique was used. As the system was engaged, a pulse was generated which sent the current thrust into a memory block. This value for equilibrium thrust was then

continually added to the controller generated Δdx_{w_cmd} for a total thrust command. The same pulse also “grabbed” the *actual* relative GPS position into memory and made it also the *desired* relative position. This made all error inputs to the control laws—the difference between desired and actual vectors—zero at system engagement. Integrators were also reset at this time. This technique allows for smooth switching from another control technique, such as hand flying or an automatic profile to rejoin to the tanker, without a step in the commands to the system as it is turned on.

PID control of position error applied to the elevator channel was found to be sufficient for the more benign maneuvers. Turns to 30° of bank with faster roll rates, however, required high gains on the derivative control to achieve desired performance. Rates up to 12 deg/sec were simulated. To preserve stability margin, additional damping was provided through wing pitch angle (θ) feedback, allowing the gains to come down and making the perturbation elevator command ($\Delta \delta e_{w_cmd}$):

$$\Delta \delta e_{w_cmd} = k_{z_p} z_e + k_{z_d} \dot{z}_e + k_{z_i} \int z_e dt + k_{z_t} \Delta \theta_w \quad (37)$$

For simulation, equilibrium values for elevator and pitch angle were again found through simulation and any errors were removed with integral action shortly after initialization. Actual elevator position was found with the addition of equilibrium and perturbation values and the application of servo dynamics.

For implementation on the Learjet, a “balance and hold” technique was used very similar to the technique for the throttles. Since the aircraft is handed to the autopilot in a trimmed (or nearly trimmed) state, the last position of the elevator at the time of autopilot engagement was added to the delta commands. Initially changing the “actual position” to “desired position” ensured that the z-axis error at engagement was zero, and again the integrator was reset.

The end result was no movement of the elevator when the system was engaged. If there was trim error at engagement, the integrator fixed it as position error built up between “current position” and the “hold current” point (relative to the tanker) where the Learjet was when engaged. Once the system was engaged at this “hold current” position, a position change was performed to go to contact, pre-contact, or the wing observation position.

The lateral channel proved the most difficult to control. PID control on position error applied directly to the ailerons is acceptable for small deviations, but with the gains high enough for tight control, the system became too aggressive with large position errors. As will be shown, some of these large errors are unavoidable during tanker maneuvers. A roll rate feedback loop was added for damping, essentially

building a roll rate command system, driven by PID control on position error.

With only a rate command system, however, there was no limit to the amount of bank that could be commanded. Large position errors, especially arising when the desired formation position was instantly changed, continually commanded an increase in bank angle. The potentially large bank angle differences between the two aircraft caused changes in the formation geometry that were fast enough to exceed the wing aircraft's ability to take the bank out without a large overshoot. With extreme lateral errors, a roll rate command system has the potential to flip the wing aircraft over if it cannot fix the position error fast enough. The lateral change from the contact position to the wing observation position is 112 feet, requiring significant transit time. Later in the design, position changes were made not with instant command changes, but with a ramp command system that drags the old commanded position to the new one. With this system, there should be no time when the wing aircraft is so far out of position that a rate command structure is incapable of stability, and a rate system should be considered in future research.

For this research, however, the controller was modified with an outer loop to command bank angle, and a dynamic saturation was added to keep the bank command of the wing aircraft within 20° of the tanker bank angle. In hindsight, this number is far too high for a bank angle difference between two aircraft in close formation. The limits were never approached in any simulation or in flight test. With position error driving bank angle, however, the tanker bank angle must be fed forward (FFD) into the bank command. Without the FFD element, the controller will not sustain a turn effectively. As the tanker banks, lateral position error develops and bank is commanded to correct it. When the position correction is made, however, the bank command returns to zero (vice staying at the tanker's bank angle--the integral effect is overly delayed), and oscillation develops. Feeding a tanker bank angle forward for the wing to match eliminates the problem.

The final lateral control technique was applied to correct for an adverse command effect. Figure 10 illustrates the problem.

Figure 10 - Adverse Roll Command at Turn Initiation

As the tanker initiates a turn to the right, the position error that develops is to the left. This causes non-minimum phase behavior in the wing aircraft's bank angle. The wing aircraft first rolls to the left, then must overcome that inertia and add the delay of removing the adverse bank before it can begin to follow the tanker's turn. The amount of adverse command seen by the controller depends on the roll rate of the tanker. For slow rolls, the tanker has time to move laterally and offset some of the adverse error. For the fastest 30° turns used in the simulations, more than 8 feet of adverse command was visible in the contact position. This magnitude of error is highly significant to a close formation controller, and would exceed the refueling boom envelope limits.

To overcome the effects of this adverse command, tanker roll rate was fed forward into the rate command portion of the control law. The gain for the roll rate FFD was optimized for the estimated most prevalent condition during refueling—15° banked turns at a roll rate of 7.5 deg/s in the contact position. This was later found in flight test to be too aggressive of a turn; less than 3 deg/s was found to be more realistic for a tanker with receivers in formation, and future research should more appropriately tune the roll rate gain. The result of the FFD control is a slight blending of the bank for the wing aircraft as it waits for the desired position to move back to the right in Figure 10 before matching the lead aircraft's bank in the turn. Allowing the tanker's bank angle to get slightly ahead does cause some dynamics that result in an overshoot to the outside of the turn. The final control law for commanded wing bank angle was found through:

$$\varphi_{w_cmd} = \varphi_L + k_{y_p} y_e + k_{y_D} \dot{y}_e + k_{y_I} \int y_e dt \quad (38)$$

This bank command was first saturated to remain within 20° of the lead aircraft, then differenced with the actual wing bank angle to find wing bank angle error (φ_{w_e}). A gain (k_{φ_e}) was applied to the bank error to generate the amount of desired roll rate (p) to correct the error in bank. Lead roll rate was added, FFD to this desired rate. The wing roll rate error was then found with:

$$p_{w_e} = k_{\varphi_e} \varphi_{w_e} + k_{p_L} p_L - p_w \quad (39)$$

The commanded aileron angle was proportional to this error in rate:

$$\delta a_{w_cmd} = k_{p_e} p_{w_e} \quad (40)$$

This value was again treated as a delta value, and the current position of the ailerons at the moment of engagement was added to the delta command to eliminate

initialization errors. Any mismatch in aileron rigging (or errors from the pilot not centering the stick at engagement) were quickly removed by integration.

Table 2 summarizes the gains selected for the wing aircraft controller with all distances in feet, thrust in pounds, and angles in degrees.

Table 2. Wing Aircraft Gains

Gain	$k_{x,P}$	$k_{x,D}$	$k_{x,I}$	$k_{z,P}$	$k_{z,D}$	$k_{z,I}$	$k_{z,\theta}$
Value	150	300	20	0.6	0.4	0.08	-2
Gain	$k_{y,P}$	$k_{y,D}$	$k_{y,I}$	$k_{\phi,e}$	$k_{p,L}$	$k_{p,e}$	
Value	0.3	0.8	0.03	2.5	1.5	-3	

6. RESULTS

Simulation Results

Simulations were performed for turns of 15° and 30° of bank in both directions for all three formation positions. The lead aircraft roll rate was 4 deg/s. Initial simulations had been performed at 7.5 deg/s, but flight test showed that 3-4 deg/s was a more realistic roll rate for a tanker with receivers in formation. All possible position changes were accomplished during straight and level flight and during established turns. Higher roll rates, higher bank angles, and maneuvers with the lead aircraft initiating a turn while the wingman was actively changing positions were investigated for controller sensitivity and robustness. Varying levels of turbulence, noise, and time delays were also investigated during all phases. The wing aircraft was stable during all simulations, except when increasing disturbances to extremes to examine the controller's stability limits.

Figure 11 shows a representative turn, with flight test noise from the actual system added in the second column to show its effects. The wing aircraft is in the contact position. For all of the turns, the x-error channel (throttle) is tightly controlled. The y-error is from the desired position to the Learjet, so as the tanker banks to the right, the initial error is to the left.

This initial excursion in the lateral error during turns is due to the adverse command that is generated by the geometry change explained in Figure 10. It is not desirable to correct this error. To do so, the receiver would have to initially turn opposite the direction of the tanker, then quickly reverse the turn direction. Pilots prefer to accept the initial error and

Figure 11 – Simulated 15 Degree Right Banked Turn in Contact Position

merely delay the turn slightly. Vertical error is also shown (where z is positive down, note that Figure 12 depicts the inverse of z and x for ease of illustration). In Figure 11, the error in the z-channel indicates the controller gets slightly low as the tanker begins to pull away until the error integration adds enough elevator to keep up with a steady state turn. Likewise, on the rollout, the controller starts high (too much residual back stick from the integrator), and moves down over time. The 15° turn is the heart of the controller's envelope, but the controller should be capable of effective station keeping for up to 30° turns. The need to use bank angles beyond the planned 15° will occasionally arise during refueling operations. Figure 12 shows the boom envelope encompassing the position track of the wing aircraft during a roll into and out of 30° of bank.

Figure 12 - Track of Wing Aircraft in Contact, 30° Bank Roll In and Roll Out, Shown with Boom Limits

The gains were relaxed to the present state to balance stability margin and performance, with some extra pad for unknowns. Table 3 summarizes the maximum position error for various maneuvers performed in simulation. The wing observation position was defined on the right of the tanker, so left turns represent turns away from the wingman

and right turns are into the wingman.

Table 3. Simulated Position Errors During Turns

Position	Bank	Max Pos. Error (ft)		
		Roll in or Roll Out		
		X	Y	Z
Contact	15°	0.3	-3.8	-1.2
	30°	0.9	5.0	-4.5
Pre-Contact	15°	0.3	4.0	-1.2
	30°	1.1	4.4	-4.5
Wing Obs.	15° Left	-1.9	4.6	5.7
	15° Right	-1.7	2.9	-5.4
	30° Left	2.5	7.3	-9.9
	30° Right	2.6	6.6	-9.3

Note that the longer the lever arm is from the tanker to the receiver, the more difficult the control is for a paradigm that maintains formation geometry. The wing observation position is 112 feet from the tanker GPS antenna, and when the tanker banks 30°, the desired wing observation position moves up/down 56 feet.

The contact position limits were defined by the boom envelope and were not exceeded short of large turns with thunderstorm level turbulence applied. There was no collision potential in the pre-contact position unless well forward, so the only required position limit of +10 feet in the x-direction was met. The collision potential can exist in the wing observation position laterally on both sides (if other wingmen are present), so a 10 foot limit in the positive and negative y-directions is desired in wing observation. The control use for all maneuvers did not saturate in rate or position with the exception of thrust, where both idle and military power were required to change airspeed when in the wing observation position during aggressive turns.

Position changes were also simulated, made in a square horseshoe fashion while refueling. For instance, from the contact position the wing aircraft first backs up and descends to the pre-contact position, then moves straight across laterally until wingtip clearance is assured before moving forward and up into the wing observation position, as shown in Figure 13.

Figure 13 -- Formation Position Change

Initially, the “corners” were commanded as desired formation positions. The wing aircraft would see position error to the new corner and fly there as a waypoint. The instant position step error, however, caused large overshoots at the “corners” due to the integration of position error for the entire time it took the aircraft to reach the next waypoint. To alleviate this, blended commands were designed to drag the desired position along the route of flight for the position change. To accomplish this in the VSS computer, a “go to” command was available to the flight test engineer (FTE) in the Learjet. Upon any change of the “go to” command, an integrator was reset which essentially operated as a clock. The number integrated was one over the time desired for each leg of the position change (30 seconds per leg was used as an operationally representative speed). The integrator clock output was saturated between zero and one, and used with a cosine function to generate a smooth curve from 0 to 1 that began and ended gently. This number was multiplied by the desired position vector of the “go to” position, and the reverse (sloped from 1 to 0) was multiplied by the position the Learjet was moving from. The two vectors were added together, and the result was a smoothly blended drag of the desired position vector. Logic was created in the software for to compensate for potential position selection errors by the FTE. For example, in Figure 13, if the wing aircraft was in the contact position (1), a selection of wing observation (4) would automatically go through pre-contact (2) and the back corner (3). A fifth “hold current” position was selected for use in system initialization, and any position could be directly flown to after a position hold.

Figure 14 shows the position vector from the tanker to the Learjet during a simulated 30° banked turn while accomplishing a position change from the contact position to wing observation. Simulation results for all position changes during straight and level flight look similar, and all are within the safe requirement for tanker operation.

Figure 14 – Simulated Position Change During Turn

Turbulence was applied as an indicator of robustness during all phases of simulation, but did not significantly impact actual controller performance. Light turbulence always caused less than 1 foot of position error in all three directions. For all levels of turbulence, random position errors were noted, but stability was never affected. Figure 15 shows the simulated performance of the controller in the contact position during straight and level flight in thunderstorm level turbulence.

The magnitude of the turbulence induced errors could cause the controller to exit the boom envelope during turns of more than 15° of bank. This was considered acceptable since Air Force aircraft are prohibited from intentionally flying in thunderstorms, and the baseline capability to refuel there straight and level exists if required for emergency situations.

Figure 15 – Simulated Straight and Level Flight with Turbulence

The addition of noise to the system caused the derivative control to make random inputs to the control surfaces. The impact of the noise was on the order of 2-4 degrees of deflection on the control surfaces. This was assumed to be negligible; however, ground testing later showed this assumption to be false. Filters were added just prior to flight testing to reduce noise effects until they were no longer noticeable in the cockpit.

For the simulation, the performance limits of the controller were first explored through increases in the lead aircraft’s bank angle. Tanker roll rates set to 10 deg/s (very abrupt for formation flying), and the tanker was simulated through 60° banked turns. At these bank angles and rates, the integral action of the controller that puts in the steady state elevator angle is slow, and the wing aircraft dropped to 10 feet “low” in the tanker body frame. Thirty seconds were required to get up to within 2 feet of the desired position. Though this is acceptable for a fringe capability, when the tanker rolls out the integral action takes time to remove the elevator command and the wing aircraft gets 25 feet high, likely causing collision. Turns with slower turn rates do not cause this problem, as the integral action has time to remove the additional elevator required in the turn. Realistically, the controller can handle turns to the bank angle limits of the aircraft, but not when combined with faster roll rates. The limits reached were collision potential, however, not stability.

The controller was found to be sensitive to roll rate increases, especially in the wing observation position where faster roll rates result in large vertical position deviations. Instability can be forced with high enough rates. However, rolls faster than a maximum of 12 deg/s were found to be unrealistic. For example, referring back to Figure 10, the adverse error (desired position left of the wing aircraft) will reach the lateral boom limit on the roll in if the wing aircraft does not begin the turn by rolling left, the wrong direction. Since tankers would either force boom release or break the boom every time they turned at these rates, no value was seen in simulating beyond a limit of 12 deg/s. Realistically, operational tankers with receivers connected typically roll at just under 3 deg/s. With a 12 deg/s roll rate and the wing aircraft in the observation position inside of the turn (the most sensitive position), the controller can handle up to 38 degrees of bank. Beyond that, stability begins to be in question, and the settling times are unacceptable. Up to 50 seconds on the roll out of a 43° banked turn. Again, these simulations were performed to explore sensitivity and robustness, and were done with fast roll rates that continued well beyond the planned 15 degrees of bank used in normal refueling tracks.

The complexity of the commands was also increased to test the limits of the controller by combining tasks. The most

complex simulation consisted of a position change commanded in thunderstorm level turbulence with the lead aircraft turning into the wingman with 30° of bank just as the wing aircraft reached the inside “corner” of the maneuver. In all cases, the controller retained stability and quickly corrected to the desired position after the change in formation geometry.

Flight Test Results

The controller was flight tested in October, 2005 at Edwards Air Force Base. A USAF C-12 simulated a tanker, with GPS measurements and attitude information (from the MEMS IMU) transmitted over a commercial datalink. This data was transmitted to Calspan’s Variable Stability System Learjet, simulating an unmanned receiver. The raw GPS measurements from both aircraft were combined, and the relative differential solution was calculated and sent to the VSS computer. The control algorithm was installed in the VSS computer, where it scheduled the flight controls and the throttles. Seven formation sorties were flown as part of a Test Management Project for the USAF Test Pilot School.

The flight test matrix that was flown started with straight and level flight in the contact, pre-contact, and wing observation positions. Additional intermediate positions were also used as a safety buildup before moving all the way in to the contact, where there was only 5 feet of nose-tail separation. Turning flight was also performed in each position, with 15 and 30 degree banked turns in both directions. Formation position changes were performed in both directions for all possible position changes. The position changes were repeated during 15 and 30 degree banked turns in both directions and while straight and level. Turns were also initiated and completed while the wing aircraft was moving between positions to introduce additional dynamics.

Overall, the system performed very well, and demonstrated the capability to refuel off of a KC-135 or KC-10 aircraft during straight and level flight, or when established in turns up to 30 degrees of bank. Rolling maneuvers did not meet expectations and are discussed below. All position changes were performed safely and efficiently. Safety or stability was never in question. Figure 16 shows a ten minute record of data in the contact position. The red lines are an approximation of the boom envelope limits.

Data: Flight Test
13 Oct 05
10,000 ft, 190 KIAS

Figure 16 – Straight and Level Performance

The mean radial error for the ten minute run was 1.33 feet, and no radial error was observed outside of 4 feet. This is well within the KC-135 boom envelope, which is smaller than that of the KC-10. The data appears noisy due to the long recording time. When stretched out, the data shows a very stable platform that was flown comparatively to an experienced pilot who is not suffering effects from night, weather, or fatigue. Station keeping in the pre-contact and wing observation positions was not significantly different. Note that the majority of the error exists in the lateral (y-axis) direction. Figure 17 shows representative error during a turn to 15 degrees of bank.

Though this turn was acceptable, the lateral control did not meet expected results. During rolling maneuvers, the controller (in the configuration actually tested) sometimes exceeded the notional boom envelope. This occurred in 1 out of 4 turns to 15 degrees of bank, as well as all of the

Data Basis: Flight Test
Date: 14 Oct 05
10,000 ft, 190 KIAS

Figure 17 – 15 Degree Turn in Contact for 60 Seconds

turns to 30 degrees of bank that were not performed with unusually slow roll rates. Error was noted after any abrupt rolling or abrupt roll reversals from the tanker. Figure 18 illustrates the problem. The autopilot on the lead aircraft was malfunctioning, and a very slow (about one degree per second) roll to 25 degrees was performed, followed by an abrupt reversal of about 8 degrees. The lateral limits of the boom were exceeded, but the aircraft was well controlled for the rest of the turn. At the rollout, a higher roll rate and slight reversal had the same effect.

Figure 18 – Turn in Contact, Failed Due to Reduction in Lateral Design Gains

Three factors caused the unpredicted error. IMU failure and a malfunctioning throttle servo contributed a small amount, but the primary source of error was a last minute erroneous decision to reduce the lateral design gains.

The heading and pitch angles from the MEMS IMU on the lead aircraft were unusable. The IMU had a firmware malfunction which allowed an undesired magnetometer “correction” to be applied when heading uncertainty reached 8 degrees. The end result was a 30 to 40 degree error applied at random times during the sortie. Bank angle and rate were unaffected.

To compensate for the hardware failure, the value for pitch angle (θ) was changed to a constant. Analysis showed an extremely small change in pitch (less than a degree) for 30 degree banked turns. The constant assumption is not only valid, it is recommended to be kept even when the IMU parameters are available. The cost for not using pitch angle is only about 3 inches of steady state error in turns, but the gain is the elimination of all noise from the pitch channel. If the capability to refuel in a climb or descent is desired (a capability rarely used operationally), then pitch angle must be retained.

Heading angle was replaced with a software estimator. Using constant g (32.2 ft/s^2), true airspeed based on our design point, and the average daily temperature during the test, the lead aircraft bank angle (ϕ) was first converted to turn rate (ω):

$$\omega = \frac{g \tan \phi}{V_T} \quad (41)$$

Turn rate was then integrated to produce a change in heading, and the flight test engineer was provided with a “sync” button used to initialize the lead heading at the beginning of each sortie to the current wing heading state. Special care was taken with magnetic heading (in the Learjet) versus true heading (in the C-12), and in keeping the integrated solution between the values of 0-360 degrees, as expected for a compass value. This solution was found to drift unacceptably due to IMU installation error and trim errors in the C-12. The wings-level bank angle varied from +5 to -4 degrees from run to run due to the poor precision of the MEMS and expected differences in trim thrust between the engines of the C-12. A correction factor ($\Delta\phi_L$) was introduced that would keep the tanker heading estimate (ψ_{L_est}) near that of the Learjet over time by slowly correcting the bank angle:

$$\Delta\phi_L = 0.4(\psi_W - \psi_{L_est}) \quad (42)$$

The correction to the lead aircraft’s bank angle made the heading estimate correct over time without inducing undue responsiveness from the wing aircraft maneuvers. The value of 0.4 was found empirically with flight test data from the first two sorties. With this short term fix, the flights were able to resume completely without input from any of the crew members except for the “go to” selections. Some

“wander” from the heading estimate increased the difficulty for the controller, and some error shown in each of the plots is due to this effect. One degree of heading wander generates 1 foot of error in the pre-contact position, plus the dynamic effects of trying to correct it. Again, for future testing, a higher fidelity sensor for the lead aircraft attitude is recommended. A rate gyro would be more appropriate than the MEMS.

The second error source was a malfunctioning throttle servo. Though the same signal was sent to both engines, the right throttle servo had a significantly higher breakout force required to induce motion. As the throttle command was reduced, the left throttle came back farther than the right. The resulting thrust asymmetry caused a left yaw, which increased lateral error, but also caused an increase in aft position error. This was countered with a power increase, but the left engine moved farther forward than the right, this time inducing right yaw, etc. Twice during flight test this effect coupled into a sustained oscillation that took approximately 30 seconds to dampen out. Some of the lateral error in all maneuvers was due to engine thrust asymmetry.

The final error source, and by far the most significant, was a reduction in the lateral design gains. When the system was installed and ground tested, several integration issues arose. One of these issues was chatter in the yoke in the lateral direction. This was mis-analyzed as noise being amplified through the derivative control. To eliminate the suspected noise problem, the total loop gain in the aileron channel was reduced to 30% of the design value, resulting in one third of the planned amount of aileron used for all maneuvers. This reduction decreased the aircraft’s initial roll rate at the beginning of rolling maneuvers, and made it slow to roll out of turns as well. The reduction of lateral control authority was the dominant source of lateral error. Later analysis showed that the chatter was not a simple noise problem after all. The DGPS position information missed an update (sometimes several) every second. The exact source of this error was never determined. The DGPS Kalman filter updates at 1 Hz, and the datalink also has a logic cycle at 1 Hz, both are likely candidates.

The DGPS provided updates at 20 Hz. Faster performance was inhibited by the datalink, which could not handle a higher flow rate. The VSS scheduled the flight control surfaces at 100 Hz. The result was a stepped appearance in the data as shown in Figure 19.

Filtering was performed on the data, but small “flat spots” still existed. The impact of the missed data was not immediately recognized. During flight in only one formation position, the differences in position error were minor and went unnoticed. However, when position

changes were commanded, the desired position began moving during each epoch, but the current position vector stopped moving once every second. This caused a direction change in the error going to the control laws—the flat spot

Figure 19 - DGPS Updates

became a corner, with two changes in the slope of the data applied to the derivative control. This generated a 1 Hz pulse in the channel of motion—aileron when moving sideways, throttle when moving longitudinally. Figure 20 shows an example from early in the flight test of this error that was extreme enough to trigger a safety trip and disengage the controller.

Figure 20 – Impact of Missed DGPS Updates

The end result was that the suspected random noise problem turned out to be something that could be fixed, and the decision to decrease the lateral gains was a mistake. A software patch was created which looked for the flat spots in the DGPS data and predicted the next step based on the last two. This fix worked for single time step missed updates, but it did not solve the problem when several

epochs were missed. To solve this, the filter structure was changed. The initial filter structure operated on the DGPS data as soon as it was received, as shown in Figure 21.

It is imperative that the IMU filters be up front, or the noise in the signals will be amplified in the coordinate transformation. The small errors in the differential position, however, are only accounted for differently by transforming them, and there is therefore no requirement to filter early. Delaying this filtering until after the current and desired position vectors have been subtracted allowed the filters to operate on the corners that were caused by the apparent closure and opening between the aircraft and its desired position.

Figure 21 – Old Filtering Paradigm

The predictive filter and the change in the basic filter structure solved the problem of the missed DGPS updates. However, the controller gains were not reset. The Learjet was only available for nine workdays, and this included system installation, ground testing, and the 7 sorties. Multiple hardware failures kept the team from investigating the problem until it was too late in the test window to restart the test matrix. (a step required for safety following any gain changes). The filter structure was changed, but design gains were not reinstated, resulting in the lateral errors seen during rolling maneuvers.

Two additional control concepts were considered, but not analyzed in this research due to time constraints. The first was to feedback lateral position error to the rudder. The aileron control must go through an additional integration before actually moving the aircraft laterally. Aileron first must develop bank, which slowly develops turn rate, which then slowly develops lateral correction. If the rudder was used, turn rate is increased directly, with potentially faster results and tighter control.

The second suggestion found for future research was to stop integrating error in the lateral channel during rolling

maneuvers. This could be easily accomplished with a simple switch to turn off the integrator when the lead aircraft roll rate exceeded a certain threshold. This compensation would prevent much of the second overshoot seen in this research during rolling maneuvers.

Aside from the non-optimal design gains, the controller performed quite well. By the last 3 test flights, the controller was turned on shortly after takeoff, and the pilots were hands free for nearly the entire 2 hour duration, suffering about 3 drop-offs per flight on average (a DGPS initialization problem required a restart once every hour, the VSS crashed twice, and there were a couple of random disconnects that were not resolved).

Position changes, both straight and level and turning were uneventful, and the controller was capable of safely maintaining position throughout normal refueling operations. Space does not permit many of the flight test results to be displayed here, but Figure 22 shows essentially all of the elements the controller was designed to do: the Learjet is in the contact position, and the tanker rolls into a 30 degree bank under the assumption that extra bank was required for a reason such as an airspace concern. A slower roll rate was used for this turn. During the turn, the Learjet is commanded to move around the “horseshoe” to the wing observation position.

Figure 22 – 30 Degree Turn in Contact, Followed by a Position Change to Wing Observation (in the turn)

As shown, all errors are well within acceptable parameters for safe and efficient automated refueling, and they are significantly better when the maneuver is performed at the planned 15 degrees of bank or straight and level. Turns initiated while the Learjet was moving between positions were found not to significantly influence the performance.

7. CONCLUSION AND LESSONS LEARNED

A proportional plus integral plus derivative controller on position error was designed. Wing aircraft feedback elements of pitch angle, bank angle and roll rate were included, as well as lead aircraft feed forward elements of roll rate and bank angle. The tanker body frame was selected for control after investigation of the results of wing body frame, wing wind frame, and formation frame control. The result was a controller capable of producing the actuator commands for a Learjet performing the elements of aerial refueling (not considering the rejoin or departure). Gains were optimized to meet the station keeping requirements in the three refueling formation positions while preserving stability margin. Formation position change capability was developed. The controller was tested by simulation and performance was assessed. Sensitivity and robustness were investigated through the addition of turbulence, noise, and time delay disturbances and an exploration of the controller limitations such as maximum bank angle and roll rate.

The controller was installed on a Learjet aircraft for flight test in formation with a C-12 in October of 2005. Flight test was performed with a reduced set of gains in the lateral channel due to suspected sensor noise difficulty, which was later resolved to be a DGPS datalink dropout problem. After the problem was found and resolved, there was insufficient time to test the true gains. The set that was tested was very effective at all refueling tasks in straight and level flight and established in turns, but suffered from lateral overshoot during roll-ins and roll-outs at moderate to high roll rates that could cause a brief disconnect during refueling. Safety and stability were never in question.

Several lessons were learned during this investigation. Sensor noise from the IMU was effectively filtered without significant impact on control. Noise from the IMU getting magnified through the derivative portion of the system was one of the most significant concerns for the paradigm of tanker body frame control. The success of this project validated the design technique of the system.

Adjustable filters and gains were essential for a developing control program, with the associated modeling and simulation on site. Having a flexible system to incorporate changes and enough time for some significant data analysis

in between sorties is also critical. The time compression in this project led to a significant reduction in performance.

Backup modes and capabilities should be designed into the controller. This project demonstrated control with only lead aircraft bank angle and the DGPS information at times, and even the bank angle is not required for straight and level refueling. Having system experts on site and backup parts helped with some of the hardware failures.

Lastly, for future control designs, consideration should be given to using rudder for lateral position error correction. Also, investigation should be made into not integrating lateral error during rolling maneuvers, and future designs must be robust enough to handle data dropouts and incomplete information. Moving the position error filters just prior to the derivative control assisted in this.

There are many methods for automated control of formation flight. This paper details one suggestion, and develops a controller that provided a safe, stable demonstration of formation flight control as a stepping stone toward fully automated aerial refueling.

Calspan was instrumental in this project, especially with the integration of the control system into the VSS. AFIT support was also critical, handling all of the DGPS considerations. AFRL provided financial support, as well as the USAF Test Pilot School.

Figure 23 - Test Aircraft

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